

Process configurations for emission control: CESAR1 emission behavior in biomass combustion gas treatment

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the emission behavior of CESAR1 solvent in a pilot-scale carbon capture unit at a biomass-fired power plant, with focus on the effects of operational configurations on amine emissions. We demonstrate that wash column parameters, including water wash flow, wash column temperature, and acid wash pH, have a significant impact on emissions.

The application of a solvent filter proved highly effective in limiting emissions by preventing the buildup and release of degradation byproducts. While activating the intercooler had a minimal direct effect on amine emissions under the conditions studied, it led to increased impurity concentrations in the CO₂-rich stream. This may indicate a redistribution of volatile compounds within the process. Additionally, a change in flue gas concentration was linked to higher emission levels, particularly of 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) and piperazine (PZ), underscoring flue gas content as a key factor driving solvent losses.

These findings highlight the intricate nature of amine emissions and provide valuable insights into the crucial role of optimizing operational conditions in enhancing emission control and system performance.

Nomenclature

Abbreviations

CCUS	Carbon capture, utilization, and storage
CDR	Carbon dioxide removal
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
BECCS	Bioenergy and carbon capture and storage
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
IC	Absorber Intercooler
PTR-ToF-MS	Proton Transfer Reaction Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometer
MTU	Mobile Test Unit
LVR	Lean Vapor Recompression
m/z	mass-to-charge ratio of an ion

Compounds

AMP	2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol
PZ	Piperazine
MEA	Monoethanolamine
MNPZ	N-nitrosopiperazine
DNPZ	Dinitrosopiperazine
LUT	2,4-lutidine
DMOZD	4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazolidinone
N-methyl AMP	2-methyl-2-(methylamino)-1-propanol
TMOZD	3,4,4-trimethyl-2-oxazolidinone
DMHTBI	4,4-dimethyl-1-hydroxytertiobutyl-2-imidazolidinone
AMPAMP	2-[(2-amino-2-methylpropyl)amino]-2-methyl-1-propanol
DMOZD	4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazolidinone
EDA	Ethylenediamine
FPZ	1-formylpiperazine

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(continued)

AEP	N-(2-aminoethyl) piperazine
2-imid	2-imidazolidone
PZ-NO ₂	N-Nitropiperazine
N-methyl PZ	N-MethylPiperazine
NPIP	N-Nitropiperidine
DFP	1,4-diformylpiperazine
DAEP	1,4-di(2-aminoethyl) piperazine
DMP	N,N-dimethylpiperazine
DMO	4,4-dimethyloxazolidine

1. Introduction

Anthropogenic climate change is evident through alterations of weather patterns and climatic extremes worldwide [1], highlighting the need for mitigation. Carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) technologies offer a promising approach to reducing emissions and achieving climate neutrality. Capturing CO₂ from industrial point sources is essential in reducing emissions from hard-to-abate sectors and for achieving the global climate goals in the coming decades [2].

In 2022, the power industry accounted for 12.67 GtCO₂eq or 38.1% of the total greenhouse gases emitted globally [3,4]. Given the sector's substantial contribution to global emissions, renewable solutions have been increasingly deployed. Biomass serves two primary functions in mitigating climate change. First, its growth removes CO₂ from the atmosphere, which is stored for varying periods, depending on harvest, enabling carbon dioxide removal (CDR). Secondly, it can serve as a direct substitute for fossil fuels, particularly in energy production [5,6].

In Denmark, a significant part of fossil fuel consumption in electricity and heating production has been replaced with solid biofuels (biomass) since 1990 [7]. Since then, the share of renewable energy in gross energy consumption (excluding international transport) has increased from 5.8% to 45.2% in 2023.

Although biomass is considered a carbon-neutral energy source [8], the implementation of carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies in bioenergy-based power plants can result in the production of carbon-negative energy [9]. Bioenergy and carbon capture and storage (BECCS) presents a feasible strategy for CO₂ mitigation and is estimated to reduce CO₂ emissions by approximately 700 g/kWh of energy generated [10,11].

As of July 2024, three industrial-scale BECCS facilities are operating globally. The most prominent one is Archer Daniels Midland (ADM), Illinois Industrial, which captures approximately 1 Mtpa CO₂ and injects it into Mt. Simon Sandstone, a deep saline formation [12]. Beyond existing operations, commercial interest in BECCS is expanding. Notably, in Scandinavia, Microsoft signed offtake agreements for two CCS energy projects: one in Denmark with Ørsted (3.67 million tons over 10 years), and another in Sweden with Stockholm Exergi (3 million tons).

A critical aspect of scaling BECCS for industrial deployment is evaluating the various carbon capture technologies. Ganeshan et al. [13] reported that various technologies have been tested at different Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), with chemical CO₂ capture representing the most mature technology, currently achieving TRL 9.

Among carbon capture technologies, amine-based chemical absorption is the most mature technology, with Monoethanolamine (MEA) being the most studied solvent [14]. MEA is regarded as the benchmark for amine capture, due to its rapid reaction kinetics with CO₂, along with its widespread application and well-understood performance characteristics [15–18]. However, the drawbacks of the solvent include high energy consumption for solvent regeneration, fast degradation, and corrosion rates [18–22].

Alternative solvents are being developed to optimize CO₂ capture, with CESAR1 being a promising alternative to MEA. The CESAR1 solvent, an aqueous solution of 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP)

promoted with piperazine (PZ), is widely regarded as the new benchmark solvent [23,24]. This is attributed to its high CO₂ loading capacity, low heat of absorption, and, in some cases, lower energy consumption compared to MEA [25,26].

Although the CESAR1 solvent has shown to be less susceptible to thermal and oxidative degradation than MEA [18], its susceptibility towards degradation remains an issue [27–29]. However, Moser et al. [30] found that MEA presents a non-linear self-acceleration degradation behavior, whereas CESAR1 experiences a slower, linear degradation rate.

Solvent degradation, due to oxidative or thermal degradation, is a growing concern as it can result in process efficiency loss, material corrosion, and emission of potentially hazardous byproducts [17]. Some of the amine byproducts can be highly volatile and can escape the system with the depleted gas stream, into the atmosphere [31,32]. Furthermore, the solvent amines can also be volatile and contribute to potential amine emissions. Morlando et al. [33] report that AMP is found to be more volatile than MEA, whereas PZ exhibits lower volatility than both [34–36]. However, Moser et al. [37] found that solvent aging also affects the volatility of solvent amines, with AMP emissions being 50% lower in very aged solvent compared to fresh solvent. By contrast, no significant changes were observed for PZ.

One of the main concerns related to CESAR1 solvent emissions is the potential formation of nitrosamines, as PZ is known to undergo nitrosation. This reaction can be triggered by oxidative degradation or exposure to nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) being present in the flue gas. The predominant nitrosamine formed is N-nitrosopiperazine (MNPZ), alongside smaller amounts of dinitrosopiperazine (DNPZ) [33]. The emission of nitrosamines is of significant concern because they are known to be carcinogenic.

Several methods are used to mitigate the emission of amines and their byproducts, including water wash systems (singular or multiple stages), acid scrubbing, and vapor-phase separation. Although amine degradation byproducts are generally water-soluble, a water wash alone has only a limited effect on gas-phase emissions, typically removing about 20% of these compounds [38]. In contrast, acid-based scrubbing has proven to be a more effective method for impurity removal [22,39–41]. Additionally, utilizing a dry bed at the top of the absorber has been shown to significantly reduce emissions [37]. Furthermore, Liu et al. [42] found that the operating parameters of the carbon capture plant influence the reduction of amine aerosol emissions. Some studies have indicated that the employment of absorber intercooling (IC) can further influence emissions [22,42,43]. However, currently, there are limited studies on the utilization of advanced process configurations in treating CESAR1 emissions.

In this work, we investigate how operational parameters influence amine-related emissions from a pilot-scale CO₂ capture plant, using the CESAR1 solvent, receiving flue gas from a biomass-fired power plant. The effectiveness of different acid wash concentrations in reducing CESAR1 solvent degradation product in the depleted gas stream is evaluated. Particular focus was given to the performance of weaker acids and the duration for which they remain active before being neutralized. The effects of implementing an absorber intercooler, an activated carbon solvent filter, modifying the reboiler duty, and flue gas composition were evaluated for their impact on amine emissions and mitigation efficiency. The results demonstrate the connection between operational parameters and emission behavior under pilot-scale conditions.

A Proton Transfer Reaction Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometer (PTR-ToF-MS) was used to measure the solvent amines and degradation products in the gas streams in real-time. The study employed a packed-bed wash tower, equipped with a water wash and an acid wash, used for gas treatment. Additionally, the pilot was shifted from base case operation to each tested configuration. Solvent degradation products escaping with the CO₂ product were also evaluated. This study offers the first pilot-scale evaluation of CESAR1 emissions in CO₂ capture from

biomass combustion flue gas. The results provide valuable insights for advancing CO₂ capture technologies and the development of pollutant control technologies.

2. Experimental setup and methodology

2.1. Experimental system

The Technical University of Denmark (DTU), in collaboration with Pentair Union Engineering, designed and constructed a mobile carbon capture test unit (MTU). The pilot plant can capture up to 1 ton of CO₂ per day and has the ability to operate 24/7. Additionally, the unit is equipped with safety protocols that automatically halt operation if any parameter falls outside the designated thresholds. The unit served as the basis for this work.

The pilot is quite flexible and can accommodate over 20 advanced process configurations, including IC, lean vapor recompression (LVR), rich recycle split feed, and others. In the past, the plant has been used for upgrading biogas [44,45], and for post-combustion capture from a waste-to-energy plant [17,46] as well as from a cement plant [18,22,47]. Fig. 1b shows the MTU in operation at Ørsted, Skærbækværket, Denmark.

The plant consists of four modularized process skids, as shown in Fig. 1a. The lower two skids are process equipment, such as the blower, filters, heat exchangers, indicators, etc. The upper two skids consist of the four columns of the unit: an absorber and a desorber (skid B, Fig. 1a) and the wash tower and an additional column used for advanced configurations (skid A).

The columns are constructed from 316 stainless steel. A summary of the column design specifications can be found in Table 1. A highly detailed description of the pilot plant is given by Vinjarapu et al. [46].

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the flue gas enters the system and undergoes a pretreatment stage, where the gas is conditioned before it reaches the absorber. It initially passes through a knock-out drum, where excess condensation is removed. Subsequently, the gas passes through an activated carbon filter, designed to adsorb hydrogen chloride (HCl) and prevent corrosion of piping and equipment. The pressure loss of the filter ranges between 10 and 100 mbar. Following pre-treatment, the

Table 1
Summary of the design data of the pilot columns.

Parameters	Absorber	Stripper	Wash tower
Height	19.34 m	17.54 m	13.4 m
Diameter	0.217 m	0.217 m	0.215 m
Volume	778 L	632 L	680 L
Packing Height	15 m	13.9 m	8.69 m
Packing material	Flex 5/8"	Flex 5/8"	KGF 5/8"
	random	random	random
Type storage vessel	Sump	Flash vessel	Sump
Volume storage vessel	120 L	120 L	34.2 L

saturated gas is received by the blower and delivered to the absorber column.

Once the gas enters the absorber, it comes into contact with the circulating solvent. The solvent reacts with the gas, and the CO₂ is absorbed. The CO₂ loaded solvent is pumped through the main heat exchanger, where it is heated before reaching the stripper. In the stripper, the solvent is further heated, enabling CO₂ desorption. The CO₂-rich gas passes through a condenser, where water is condensed and returned to the absorber, thereby maintaining the plant's water balance.

The gas that exits the absorber column enters the wash tower from the bottom of the column. The depleted gas passes through a water wash section, where it is cooled. The collected condensate is returned to the system. Lastly, the gas passes through the acid wash section and the polishing section before exiting the system and being returned to the stack.

2.2. Wash tower column

The wash tower consists of six packed bed sections, divided into three main sections. The lower section houses a water wash with two packed beds, an acid wash in the middle with one packed bed, and a top polishing section with a final packed bed, as shown in Fig. 2.

The water wash is essential for maintaining the plant's water balance by cooling the gas exiting the absorber, keeping the outlet temperature close to the inlet temperature throughout the operation. It also

Fig. 1. a) 3D model of the capture plant. b) The MTU demonstrating at Ørsted, in Skærbækværket, Denmark.

acid (H₂SO₄). The bed was cleaned with demineralized water prior to testing throughout the gas measuring campaign. Afterwards, the bed was filled with different target acid capacities (pH 1, pH 3, pH 5), diluted down from 40 wt%.

2.5. Gas emission measurement methodology

As part of this work, DTU, in collaboration with FORCE Technologies, performed gas analysis tests. A PTR-ToF-MS was used for continuous measurements of amines and their degradation products. The PTR-ToF-MS is an instrument for real-time measurements of most organic gaseous compounds down to sub-ppb concentrations. The analyte gas enters the instrument through a heated inlet into the reaction chamber, where it is ionized by proton transfer reaction with the hydronium ion (H₃O⁺).

Ionized molecules are transferred through transfer lenses to the time-of-flight mass spectrometer, which detects the ions according to mass-to-charge ratio (*m/z*). The mass of the ion determines the time of flight, i.e. heavy ions travel more slowly than light ones. The flight time is proportional to the square root of the mass of the ion. The method is described in detail by Hansel et al. [50]. and Lindinger et al. [51].

The PTR-ToF-MS from Ionicon Analytik GmbH 4000 QB has a mass resolution of 4000 *m/Δm* 4000 at full-width-half-maximum at *m/z* 181. It was operated at a drift tube temperature of 110 °C, and the drift tube pressure was kept at 3.2 mbar, resulting in an *E/N* of 130 TD. *E/N* describes the ratio of the electric field strength in the drift tube relative to the density of molecules. *E/N* influences collisional energy and thereby the fragmentation of analytes. The PTR-ToF-MS was interfaced to the gas with a heated filter, and a 3-meter-long heated hose with silconert® coating.

The sample line was maintained at 110 °C throughout the measurement campaign to prevent condensation of water and minimize surface effects. A pump was applied to draw a carrier flow of 1–2 L/min. The sampled gas was diluted with bottled nitrogen using an internal dilution system.

The PTR-ToF-MS measurement data were processed using PTRMS Viewer v3.4.6. The concentration calculations were corrected solely by applying the instrument-specific transmission function, and no additional compound-specific calibrations were performed. Consequently, the reported concentrations are considered semi-quantitative, and relative changes are presented rather than absolute concentration values.

It is well-known that PTR-ToF-MS cannot differentiate between isomeric compounds. Consequently, signals at a specific *m/z* may correspond to one or more isomeric species. Compound assignments should be considered tentative and based on plausible molecular formulas derived from the *m/z* data, supported by previously reported compounds in the literature.

Quantitative measurements with uncertainties better than ±30% can be achieved for most organics, provided that fragmentation, deprotonation, or other artefacts do not occur, even without calibration [52]. The PTR-ToF-MS provides accurate measurements of the mass and thereby the molecular sum formula. In the assignment of signal, the isotope patterns are included in the analysis. At the applied settings, AMP is known to undergo fragmentation, while piperazine is stable and only undergoes negligible fragmentation [53,54]. Similarly, nitrosamines are also expected to fragment. The presented measurements have not been corrected for these fragmentation patterns. Despite these limitations, the PTR-ToF-MS measurements provide valuable insights into trends and relative changes in compound abundance.

The PTR-ToF-MS can measure most volatile organic compounds. During measurements, a heated filter was positioned upstream of the inlet. Due to the temperature of the filter, amines and other compounds present as aerosol particles are expected to volatilize, leading to their detection as gas-phase components in the PTR-ToF-MS analysis.

Only a few studies have employed a PTR-ToF-MS to measure amine

emissions from carbon capture plants [55–57]. However, to date, it has not yet been utilized in studies on carbon capture systems operating with CESAR1 while treating biomass-derived flue gas.

2.6. Validation of gas measurement

To ensure the reliability of the PTR-ToF-MS detected compounds, complementary sampling was conducted at the plant approximately one week prior to the PTR-ToF-MS campaign. The samples were collected using conventional sampling techniques, specifically, impinger sampling in sulfamic acid, followed by LC-MS/MS/MS analysis. All collected liquid samples were then analyzed by the SINTEF Department of Mass Spectrometry in Norway. The method is explained in detail by Dimitriadi et al. [22].

These measurements confirmed the presence of several relevant compounds, including AMP, piperazine, and MNPZ, providing independent support for the plausibility of some of the tentative PTR-ToF-MS assignments. Representative results of this complementary method are provided in the Supplementary Material.

2.7. Measured gas compounds

Amine degradation compounds are often characterized based on the conditions under which they were formulated, leading to the classification of thermal and oxidative degradation compounds. However, Morlando et al. [33] suggest that, in practice, the distinction between the two categories is not always clear. Many of the main degradation compounds of CESAR1 need both heat and an oxidizing agent to be formed.

2.7.1. Emissions from AMP

Wang [58] conducted an in-depth study into the stability of AMP, identifying acetone, 2,4-lutidine (LUT), 4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazolidinone (DMOZD), formate, oxalate, acetate, glycolate, nitrite, nitrate, and ammonia as the main products of oxidative AMP degradation. Additionally, 2-methyl-2-(methylamino)-1-propanol (commonly referred to as *N*-methyl AMP) is also considered a major degradation product formed under oxidative conditions [59].

Thermal degradation products of AMP compounds include 3,4,4-trimethyl-2-oxazolidinone (TMOZD), *N*-methyl AMP, and 4,4-dimethyl-1-hydroxytertiobutyl-2-imidazolidinone (DMHTBI). Additionally, 2-[(2-amino-2-methylpropyl)amino]-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMPAMP) and 4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazolidinone (DMOZD) are also formed under elevated temperature conditions [58,60]. In addition to solvent AMP, emissions of *N*-methyl AMP and acetone were identified during the present work. Their chemical identities and corresponding CAS registry numbers are provided in Fig. 3.

2.7.2. Emissions from PZ

The main compounds formed during the oxidative degradation of PZ include ammonia, formate, oxalate, ethylenediamine (EDA), and 1-formylpiperazine (FPZ), as well as smaller quantities of nitrate, nitrite, and acetate [61]. The main thermal degradation products of PZ are FPZ, ammonium, *N*-(2-aminoethyl) piperazine (AEP), and 2-imidazolidone (2-imid) [33,62,63].

Fig. 3. Molecular structure of measured AMP-related compounds.

Fig. 4. Molecular structure of measured PZ-related compounds.

One of the main concerns with emissions from the CESAR1 solvent is the formation of nitrosamines. This happens because piperazine (PZ) can easily undergo nitrosation, a reaction that may occur due to oxidative degradation or exposure to nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) present in the flue gas. The most common nitrosamine formed MNPZ, along with smaller amounts of DNPZ [33].

Nitramines are potentially carcinogenic compounds and may pose an even greater risk than nitrosamines [64]. Nitramines can be formed when amines react with NO_2 . In this context, the relevant nitramine is PZ- NO_2 . Additionally, Tan et al. [53] found that dinitropiperazine is formed when PZ- NO_2 is photo-oxidized. However, in this case, the formation of dinitropiperazine is highly unlikely. In addition to pure PZ, emissions of multiple above-mentioned compounds were confirmed in this study. Their chemical identities and corresponding CAS registry numbers are provided in Fig. 4.

2.7.3. CESAR1-relate emissions deriving from a combination of AMP + PZ

The combination of the solvent compounds, AMP and PZ, has previously been reported to result in the formation of additional degradation compounds [58]. These compounds include 1,4-diformylpiperazine (DFP), as a result of oxidative degradation, and 1,4-di(2-aminoethyl) piperazine (DAEP), and *N,N'*-dimethylpiperazine (DMP), as a result of thermal degradation. Furthermore, Rochelle [65] found that the oxidative degradation rate of AMP increased in the presence of PZ.

In addition to the emission of compounds related to AMP/PZ blends, Languille et al. [29] detected the emissions of formaldehyde, acetonitrile, acetaldehyde, among others, in the depleted gas stream following two wash sections. Of the degradation products emitted in the TCM's CESAR1 pilot campaign. Acetone was the most dominant. In this study, the emission of these compounds was also observed. Additional degradation products identified included acetonitrile, formamide, methylamine, morpholine, 4,4-dimethylloxazolidine (DMO), 4-acetylmorpholine, and a compound with the molecular formula $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2$. The compounds measured, in conjunction with their CAS numbers, are presented in Fig. 5.

Certain compounds, including small organic acids, ammonia/ammonium, and other volatile organic compounds, are anticipated to form in all amine-based solvents, including CESAR1 [33]. Ammonia is a byproduct of both AMP and PZ. The presence of several of these species in the depleted gas was also confirmed in this study. The compounds analyzed, along with their corresponding CAS numbers, are presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 5. Additional compounds detected in the depleted gas during the campaign.

Fig. 6. Measured general degradation compounds that are typically found or expected in AMP/PZ blends.

In addition to the above-mentioned compounds, a few unidentified emission compounds were also observed during this study. Compounds with the molecular formula of $\text{CH}_6\text{N}_3\text{O}$ or $\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$, based on mass-to-charge ratio, were also likely observed. Additionally, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{O}$ and CH_3NO_2 were also observed, with the latter presumed to be nitromethane. However, the measured amount of these compounds was low, with only $\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$ exceeding two ppb.

2.8. Data processing

During the measurement campaign, the PTR-ToF-MS continuously monitored the depleted gas stream for a total duration of seven days. Afterwards, the instrument was used to collect data from the product gas stream (CO_2 rich). The instrument was purged using nitrogen twice during this period.

The data collected was reported by the second. While measuring the depleted gas stream, the raw signal exhibited irregularities, including sharp peaks and outliers. The peaks were periodic and repeated approximately every three minutes. A definitive correlation with the plant's operational parameters (gas and liquid flows) was not identified, but the regularity of the pattern strongly suggests an underlying link. In this study, to provide a more accurate representation of the depleted gas emission data, outliers were removed, and a moving average was applied (every 240 seconds) to smooth short-term fluctuations. The data presented in this work are representative of pilot-scale measurements and can inform future modeling efforts.

3. Results

3.1. Flue gas analysis and impact on emission behavior

A detailed analysis of the composition and variability of flue gas from biomass-fired boilers, along with their impact on emission levels, is

presented. The relationship between fluctuations in flue gas composition, particularly in oxygen levels, and changes in emissions are examined. These insights highlight the impact of flue gas composition on a carbon capture system and emission outcomes.

3.1.1. Flue gas composition and variability

Throughout the campaign, the pilot plant received flue gas from Ørsted's biomass-fired boilers at Skærbækværket. To ensure continuous operation, the plant primarily operated on flue gas supplied from boiler '401', with occasional transitions to boiler '402' if needed. When both boilers were in operation, they typically ran in parallel, utilizing the same type of biomass and experiencing similar load variations.

During the gas emissions campaign, boiler '401' was ramped down due to low district heating demand, which is common towards the end of April, depending on weather conditions. As a result, the operation was then switched to boiler '402'. Fig. 7 illustrates the changes in flue gas composition during the switch on April 28th, indicated by the beige color. The exact timing of the switch is not critical, as the two boilers were operating very similarly. Ørsted reports all measured components as dry conditions at 6 % O₂ reference basis, except for O₂ and H₂O, which are reported as measured.

As seen in Fig. 7b, CO₂ levels stayed similar after the boiler change, with a slight decrease on the last day, as measured at the pilot's inlet probe. Notably, there is an inverse relationship with oxygen concentrations. This is most apparent before the boiler change. The fluctuations before the boiler change can be attributed to the load on the boiler. At high load, the O₂ content in the flue gas is lower compared to when operating at low load. A similar behavior was also observed between CO and oxygen.

When both boilers are operating in parallel, they respond similarly to

load variations. Prior to the boiler switch, the load fluctuated between high and medium levels. Following the boiler change, the operation mode was limited to low load only, as shown in Fig. 7a, where the O₂ concentration of the gas increased from 6% to 10%.

Ørsted measured concentrations at 50 °C, however, the gas reached the pilot at approximately 19 °C due to cooling of the feed pipe before the carbon capture plant. Therefore, fluctuations in the water vapor content (Fig. 7b) coming from the boiler were of limited significance for the operation of the capture plant.

Following the boiler change, SO_x concentration was reduced from 0.5 mg/Nm³ to non-detectable levels, as shown in Fig. 7f. However, NO_x exhibited the same behavior before and after the boiler change, with the concentration remaining constant at approximately 140 mg/Nm³, with minor fluctuations (Fig. 7c). Ammonia also stayed below the detection limit for most of the measurements, with only a few detection points above 0 mg/Nm³. Yet remaining below 4 mg/Nm³ (Fig. 7d).

CO concentrations also stayed at a similar level, at approximately 40 mg/Nm³, but with fewer fluctuations following the boiler change. As previously mentioned, there is an inverse relationship with oxygen, as illustrated in Fig. 8. Inverse fluctuations observed in Fig. 8, before the boiler change, which is attributed to boiler load.

3.1.2. Influence of flue gas composition on emissions

The change in flue gas composition seems to affect amine emissions. At the time of this change, the plant operated under baseline conditions with no special configurations applied. As shown in Fig. 9a, the shift in composition, demonstrated by oxygen concentration, was accompanied by a corresponding increase in emissions, particularly the emission of AMP, which increased by approximately 19 ppbv. PZ's concentration increased approximately 1.5 ppbv, representing nearly a fivefold

Fig. 7. Flue gas concentrations during the gas measurement campaign, including a boiler change. a) Oxygen concentration in (%), b) The concentration of H₂O (boiler stack) and CO₂ (MTU), c) NO_x, d) NH₃, e) CO and f) SO₂ in mg/Nm³.

Fig. 8. Inverse relationship of O₂ [%] and CO [mg/Nm³] in the flue gas due to boiler loading, during measurements.

increase from its initial level, while MNPZ and DNPZ increased by approximately 1.5 ppbv and 0.5 ppbv, respectively (Fig. 9a).

Similar behavior was exhibited by methyl-AMP, PZ-NO₂, acetylmorpholine, and a signal tentatively assigned to N-Nitrosopiperidine. The remaining measured compounds do not have a significant influence on the flue gas composition shift.

Overall, it is observed that flue gas composition influences the emission of some of the amine compounds. As shown in Fig. 9b, a positive correlation was observed between AMP and flue gas oxygen concentration (which indicates the flue gas composition change), when excluding measurements affected by operational changes. Data from plant disturbances, like acid washes at pH 1 and 3 or solvent filter shutdown, were excluded to minimize confounding effects and better

characterize the intrinsic relationship between AMP and flue gas composition.

The results suggest that under stable operating conditions, variations in AMP are closely linked to fluctuations in the flue gas (Fig. 9b). Similar behavior is also observed with PZ, as illustrated in Fig. 9c. However, PZ emissions remained much lower than AMP emissions throughout the whole campaign.

The observed increase in emissions following the boiler change could be attributed to several factors. While aerosols could be a potential cause, it is unlikely, as SO_x levels decreased after the swift, as shown in Fig. 7f. Likewise, NO_x levels, which can influence emissions, remained unchanged (Fig. 7c). Other operating parameters, including inlet and absorber temperature, were stable throughout the change, ruling out process disturbances as the main driver. The most likely explanation for the increased emissions is that the change in gas composition possibly resulted in a slight foaming effect at the top of the absorber column. Foaming tendency can increase solvent carryover, which could explain the rise in observed solvent and solvent-related emissions. This mechanism is consistent with the overall trends measured and provides a plausible explanation for the observed emission increase.

3.2. Wash column operation and impact on emissions

The operational parameters of the wash tower, including pump stability, wash column temperature, and acid concentration, were evaluated for their impact on emission behavior. The analysis highlights how fluctuations in the tower impact impurity removal efficiency and emission control. The results underscore the sensitivity of emissions to operational changes in the wash tower.

3.2.1. Water wash pump fluctuations

The bottom two beds of the wash tower function as the wash section, as illustrated in Fig. 2. To achieve this, the loop is equipped with a circulation pump and a heat exchanger. During the gas measuring

Fig. 9. a) Emissions of AMP, PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ measured in ppbv (right axis) and emissions of O₂ measured in [%] (left axis), b) AMP emissions [ppbv] as a function of oxygen [%] throughout the campaign, excluding measurements affected by operational changes, c) PZ emissions [ppbv] as a function of oxygen [%] excluding measurements affected by operational changes.

Fig. 10. Flow of the water wash circulation loop pump in [kg/h] (left axis) and AMP emissions in [ppbv] (right axis) over time.

campaign, fluctuations in the pump's operation were found to influence the amine emissions, as illustrated in Fig. 10. Throughout the measuring campaign, the water wash circulation flow was maintained at $464 \text{ kg/h} \pm 3.7 \text{ kg/h}$. These minor fluctuations in flow are expected due to standard mechanical and hydraulic characteristics of the pump systems and are unavoidable.

On Fig. 10, the water wash circulation flow in kg/h (left axis) and AMP emissions in ppbv (right axis) are shown over time. A moving average (every 500 points) is used to reduce noise and make it easier to

observe overall trends over time ("Wash (Av)", Fig. 10). The blue line represents the moving average of the circulation flow, while the lighter blue shows the raw data. The red line represents the real-time AMP emissions measured at the depleted gas outlet. The shaded areas represent periods where the acid loop was active. Since the acid bed is positioned higher in the column than the water wash, its effect on gas emissions can be easily observed. As illustrated in Fig. 10, the acid loop had a significant effect on the emissions. However, the impact of the acid on the emissions will be further discussed in the following sections.

The wash section water flow is observed to be directly related to emissions. As can be seen in Fig. 10, when the flow of the water circulation increases on April 26th at 06:00 am, the emissions follow a similar trend. The effect is even more apparent while the acid loop was operating in steady operation, approximately from April 26th at 15:20 until April 27th at 07:00. During this period, AMP emissions appear to mirror the behavior of the flow rate. Besides AMP, similar behavior is observed in the emissions of PZ, MNPZ, DNPZ, PZ-NO₂, methyl-AMP, formamide, as well as the compound with the molecular formula of CH₆N₃O or C₃H₈O₂. However, due to the minimal magnitude of these changes, other factors exert a significantly greater influence on amine emissions.

3.2.2. Water wash temperature

As above mentioned, the wash column consists of several sections. The temperature of the complete wash column can be influenced by several factors, with the most significant being the acid wash loop, weather conditions, water wash cooling, and the IC. During the Skærbækværket campaign, the pilot plant was situated in a closed space, protected from the elements. That resulted in minimal to no influence of weather conditions on the plant's temperatures.

Introducing acid into the column has a cooling effect in the upper section of the wash column, in addition to reducing emissions, as shown in Fig. 11a. This is indicated by the fast drop in temperatures of the

Fig. 11. a): Raw transient data of the wash column temperature profile. b) the temperature profile of the wash tower.

upper beds of the column at 09:42, indicated by a vertical black line. The sudden reduction in the temperature of the wash tower at the onset of the acid loop occurs as the acid is not in thermal equilibrium with the plant. The acid is stored in a standalone vessel (Fig. 2) when not in use, which prevents it from being exposed to operational temperatures. The transient effect of introducing the acid on the wash tower's temperature profile is shown in Fig. 11b.

Finally, the water wash cooling is designed to cool and condense any possible vapor in the depleted gas, as required, to maintain a water balance. As expected, this results in an overall reduction in the temperature profile of the column, as illustrated in Fig. 11b.

3.2.3. Influence of wash column temperature on emissions

During the gas measuring campaign, the temperature profile of the wash tower was found to impact the emissions in the depleted gas stream. Lower temperatures resulted in reduced amine emissions, while higher temperatures led to increased emissions. The effect of the temperatures of the wash column for different compounds is shown Fig. 12. Throughout the campaign, no cooling was applied to the wash loop during the first days, with cooling becoming necessary only during the final days.

During active cooling, the water was pumped through a heat exchanger, where a controlled flow of cooling water cooled it. In Fig. 12, the period where the bed was actively cooled is indicated by the light blue color section. The effect of the active cooling of the temperature of the bottom bed of the wash tower (Bed 1) is indicated by the light blue trend. As a result of the tower's cooling, the temperature of the bed was reduced from 47 °C to approximately 27 °C.

As shown in Fig. 12a, as the temperature of the wash tower drops, a corresponding reduction in AMP emissions is observed, showing an approximate 40% decrease relative to the initial concentration. A similar trend was observed for PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ, as illustrated in Fig. 12b, with PZ exhibiting the most significant degree of influence of the temperature drop. That could potentially be due to PZ's higher emission levels, compared to MNPZ and DNPZ, which were already

detected at very low levels.

Formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, morpholine, methyl-AMP, formamide, and acetonitrile also exhibit comparable behavior, all showing a reduction following the active cooling, as shown in Fig. 12c. Additionally, acetone, PZ-related compounds such as piperidine, N-PIP, acetylmorpholine, and PZ-NO₂, as well as degradation products like NH₄⁺ and formic acid, and chemical formations CH₃NO₂ and C₃H₈O₂, all displayed temperature dependency. However, the decrease persisted only for the duration of active cooling, with emissions returning to previous levels once it was turned off.

The temperature dependency of the amine emissions was consistently observed throughout the entire campaign, but it was more evident when active cooling was in use. As previously mentioned, the acid wash affects the wash column's temperature, however, it is challenging to distinguish whether the observed reduction is due to the acid or the temperature change. Finally, the overall upward trend in emissions illustrated in Fig. 12 is attributed to the solvent filter, which is discussed in a later section.

3.2.4. Influence of acid concentrations on emissions

As discussed, the wash tower includes both a water wash and an acid wash system. The effectiveness of impurity removal for the combined water and acid wash system was evaluated. Specifically, the impact of varying acid concentrations on removal efficiency was tested by periodically switching the acid wash on and off. Continuous real-time emission measurements supported the analysis. Both the acid wash and water wash beds were in operation during the measurements. Between tests, the acid tank was drained and washed with water before being refilled with acid, containing approximately 30 kg of liquid.

Three different target acid capacities were tested: pH 1, pH 3, and pH 5. For all the tests, the acid circulation flow was kept between 200 and 222 kg/h. For the tested flow rates, the entire acid volume was circulated in under 10 minutes. The circulation pump was used to ensure thorough mixing before starting each experiment. However, this mixing process is reflected in the live measurements.

Fig. 12. Emissions [ppbv] (left axis) and temperature at the top of wash bed 1 [°C] (right axis) over time for: a) AMP, b) PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ, c) other solvent-specific degradation products. Emission measurements are considered semi-quantitative.

Fig. 13. AMP, PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ emissions [ppbv] (left axis) and pH of the acid wash (right axis) over time. Measurements are considered semi-quantitative.

3.2.4.1. High acid wash concentration evaluation (pH 1). For the first acid test, 0.1 M sulfuric acid was mixed with a target pH of approximately 1. Two tests were performed with 0.1 M acid, indicated by the orange shaded areas in Fig. 13. The first test was initiated on April 25th at 13:14 and operated continuously for approximately 4 hours, until 16:13. The pump was then turned off for approximately 4 hours and reinitiated at 20:01, running through the night and being turned off on April 26th at 06:44.

The pH of the loop is depicted in Fig. 13 by the orange line. The slight initial drop in pH immediately after the pump is started is expected, as the pipe where the pH sensor is located begins to experience flow. However, the pH stabilizes shortly after. The pH of the mixture remained relatively steady throughout the whole testing period, with an increase of 1.34 to 1.46 pH after 10 hours and 43 minutes of continuous operation.

The impact of the acid wash on the emission of solvent amines, as well as on the compounds MNPZ and DNPZ, is presented in Fig. 13. The initial emission decrease before acid circulation (April 25th from 13:14 until 16:13), can be attributed to a drop in temperature of the wash column.

The wash tower, utilizing the highly acidic solution, proved effective in reducing almost all measured emissions. In particular, after the first acid test (April 25th from 13:14 until 16:13), AMP decreased by approximately 94%, while PZ decreased by approximately 75%. Similarly, MNPZ and DNPZ decreased by approximately 87.5% and 50%,

Table 2

Compound level changes before and after the 1 pH acid test measured with PTR-ToF-MS. Measurements are considered semiquantitative.

Compound	Measurements [ppbv]		Reduction [%]
	Before acid	After acid	
NH ₄ ⁺	629.1	221.9	64.7
Acetaldehyde	74.0	18.9	74.5
Formic Acid	105.6	6.7	93.7
Acetic Acid	34.3	10.6	69.0
Methyl-AMP	2.7	0.0	98.6
Morpholine	6.1	1.7	71.9
Acetylmorpholine	1.2	0.2	85.3
Methyl-PZ	0.7	0.2	77.5
Piperidine	0.4	0.1	82.7
NPIP	7.0	0.5	92.8
PZ-NO ₂	0.6	0.1	83.8
CH ₃ NO ₂	1.5	0.6	62.9
C ₅ H ₆ O	1.3	0.3	78.7

respectively. The compounds continued to show a decrease between the acid tests. This is likely due to residual acid remaining in the packed bed, despite the absence of active liquid circulation. A similar response is also observed for most measured compounds.

While the PTR-ToF-MS measurements provide reliable insights into relative concentration changes and compound behavior, the reported values should be interpreted as semi-quantitative rather than exact absolute concentrations. A list of the changes in the measured compounds before and after the strong acid test is presented in Table 2. No change was observed in the behavior of formaldehyde, acetonitrile, formamide, acetone, dinitropiperazine, and the compound with the molecular formula CH₆N₃O or C₃H₈O₂, and therefore are not included in Table 2. It should be noted that the ion-source formation of ammonium ions in PTR-ToF-MS complicates measurements, limiting the reliable measurement of ammonium in the sample.

By the end of the run, the concentrations of the solvent amines, as well as MNPZ and DNPZ, were all measured to be near 0 ppbv. Demonstrating the effectiveness of the highly acidic solution in limiting amine emissions.

3.2.4.2. Acid wash concentration evaluation (pH 3). Following the pH 1 acid test, the acid loop was switched off and the acid was drained. The plant continued to operate without acid in the wash column for approximately 6 hours. When the emission levels started to increase, a new acid composition was mixed to achieve a target pH of 3.

The acid solution was loaded into the plant, and the circulation pump was used for mixing twice, on April 26th from 11:47 until 12:19 and from 12:36 until 13:36, as indicated by the purple-filled area in Fig. 14. Subsequently, the test was initiated on April 26th at 13:56 and operated continuously for approximately 18 hours until April 27th at 08:10, as indicated by the orange-filled area in Fig. 14. The initial pH reading at the start of the test was 2.5. Throughout the neutralization process, the pH increased gradually at first, due to the buffering of the acid solution, as illustrated for the period until 16:20, Fig. 14. As the acid became increasingly depleted, the pH began to rise more steeply, reaching a reading of 5.3 at 17:31.

For the remaining time of the experiment, the rate of pH change slowed, and the curve began to level off, indicating that all the added acid had been neutralized. The system was approaching the equivalence point, where the solution neared neutrality. By the end of the experiment, the acid reached a pH of 6.6. This suggests that the emissions and the pH were almost completely neutralized, with the acid mainly dictated by the CO₂ present (approximately 1.4 mol% in the gas phase). This case did not increase pH any further, indicating less carryover of base components from the CO₂ solvent.

As shown in Fig. 14a, the effect of the lower acid concentration didn't have a significant impact on AMP emissions, with most of the dips and spikes being due to the wash tower's circulation pump fluctuations. However, this could also be attributed to the fact that the emissions are already at low concentrations. As shown in Fig. 14b and Fig. 14c, similar behavior can be observed in most measured compounds. Particularly, PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ remained relatively stable at low concentrations throughout the test, exhibiting minimal to no detectable variation. The observed DNPZ increase at 01:30 was most likely attributable to ToF-MS remeasurement and mass calibration reattribution during that period.

3.2.4.3. Acid wash concentration evaluation (pH 5). For the final acid wash test, the acid tank was emptied, and the acid composition was mixed to achieve a target pH of 5. The solution was once again combined into a drum for pre-mixing before being added to the plant.

The acid solution was loaded into the plant. The circulation pump was used for mixing, on April 29th from 12:45 until 15:05, as indicated by the purple filled area in Fig. 15. The test was initiated immediately after mixing, on April 29th at 15:05, as noted in the orange shaded area in Fig. 15. The initial pH reading at the beginning of the test was 2.5. As

Fig. 14. Emissions [ppbv] (left axis) and acid wash pH (right axis) over time during the target pH 3 test, shown for: a) AMP, b) PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ, and c) other solvent-specific degradation products. Emission measurements are considered semi-quantitative.

expected, the acid exhibited similar behavior to the previous test (pH 3 run). However, in this case, due to the lower concentration of acid in the solution, neutralization occurred more rapidly. The pH increased quickly to approximately 4.0 after about an hour and a half of operation.

Following this, the rate of pH increase became steeper, reaching a value of roughly 8.0 by 17:42, as illustrated in Fig. 15. For the remaining of the test, the solution's pH continued to increase gradually for the remainder of the experiment, with a final value of 9.5 at the end of the test. The

Fig. 15. Emissions [ppbv] (left axis) and acid wash pH (right axis) over time during the target pH 5 test, shown for: a) AMP, b) PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ, and c) other solvent-specific degradation products. Emission measurements are considered semi-quantitative.

high pH was probably due to the excess of minor base components from the CO₂ solvent being carried over into the acid wash.

Fig. 15 demonstrates that the lower acid concentration had little influence on the amine emissions. Notably, in the case of AMP, the initial decrease in concentration was minimal. This may be attributed to several potential factors besides acid, with one of them being the active tower cooling, illustrated by the blue shaded area in Fig. 15a. AMP concentration continued to increase throughout the test, with only temporary decreases during periods with active cooling or temperature decrease, such as the one recorded on April 30th at 03:30.

PZ and DNPZ concentrations were also unaffected by the presence of acid and remained relatively constant throughout the test, exhibiting only brief declines as a result of active cooling periods, as illustrated in Fig. 15b. The concentration of MNPZ showed a decreasing trend; however, this was not related to the presence of acid and will be discussed in a later section. A similar trend was observed across most of the measured compounds, as shown in Fig. 15c.

Overall, in both tests involving low-concentration acid solutions (pH 3 and 5), the acid was quickly neutralized, with the pH rising to neutral or above within a few hours. The results show that maintaining the solution at approximately pH 3 is sufficient to reduce emissions without the need for high-concentration acid. Furthermore, utilizing a low-concentration acid would reduce the risk of corrosion due to it having fewer hydrogen ions. However, due to the low concentration, the acid was neutralized rapidly and acted more as a buffer than a reactive agent. Demonstrating little to no impact on AMP, PZ, DNPZ, or other compound concentrations. Consequently, weekend acid solutions had a negligible effect on the system's emissions or overall behavior over time. This suggests that a controlled acid dosing system, capable of maintaining a consistently low pH, could provide more consistent and effective results.

3.3. Influence of process configurations on emissions

Process configurations have a critical role in absorption efficiency and operational costs within carbon capture systems. Key parameters, such as absorber intercooling, reboiler duty, and the solvent filter, are analyzed to reveal their impact on amine emissions. The results demonstrate how operational adjustments can influence emissions and overall system behavior.

3.3.1. Influence of intercooling on temperature profiles and emission behavior

The intercooling configuration is employed to improve the solvents' affinity towards CO₂ and thereby increase the capture efficiency. This is achieved by reducing the temperature of the solvent in a selected absorber section. In the MTU, the IC can be switched between different packing beds. CO₂ absorption is an exothermic reaction, and although it occurs throughout the column, the largest temperature occurs in the middle of the column if operated optimally [66,67]. So, the IC is typically most effectively placed in the second bed.

For intercooling, a stream of solvent is withdrawn from the absorber, cooled externally, and reintroduced into the column just below the extraction point. During the emission measuring campaign, the IC was placed on the second bed of the absorber. The IC was set at 175.9 ± 2.4 kg/h, and the temperature of the solvent re-injected in the absorber was 34.15 ± 0.94 °C.

During the emissions measurements, the intercooler was deliberately activated twice, first on April 27th at 08:15, where it operated for 12 hours and 35 minutes. The intercooler was then shut down and the plant was returned to base case. It was employed then again on April 28th at 22:11, operating for 14 hours and 8 minutes. The cooling effect of the IC on the absorber temperature profile is instantaneous, as can be seen in Fig. 16a. This is indicated by the fast drop in temperatures at 22:12, as indicated by the black vertical line. The temperature drop is especially

Fig. 16. a) Raw transient data of the absorber temperature profile before and after turning on the intercooler, b) Raw transient data of the wash column temperature profile. c) The temperature profile of the wash tower.

Fig. 17. Emissions [ppbv] over time during the IC test, shown for: a) AMP, PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ, and b) other solvent-specific degradation products. Emission measurements are considered semi-quantitative.

noticeable in the absorber bed where the IC is installed, specifically at the packing heights of 5.33 m and 6.23 m.

During the campaign, the plant operated in a highly controlled environment, so the effect of intercooling on the wash tower was less pronounced than it would be in an outdoor setting. The wash tower maintained a very stable temperature profile compared to other campaigns, as wash cooling was required less frequently than in other campaigns [22,68,69]. Consequently, when intercooling was employed, the resulting temperature changes in the wash tower were minimal, as seen in Fig. 16b. As shown in Fig. 16c, approximately 2 °C reduced the wash column's temperature profile.

For the duration of the IC tests, there is a minimal to no change in the overall emissions. Fig. 17a, illustrates the emission levels of AMP, PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ. PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ display relatively steady concentrations throughout the IC testing period. There is limited to no impact of IC on the emission level. AMP exhibited a temporary increase before the IC testing. However, the growth is not attributed to the IC test itself, but rather a short-term rise in temperature in the wash tower. Additionally, it is worth noting that the IC test, illustrated in Fig. 17, was performed following the increase of oxygen concentration in the flue gas, during which emissions were generally higher. All measured compounds exhibited similarly stable trends throughout the testing period, appearing mainly unaffected by the employment of IC, as seen in Fig. 17b. The impact of the IC on compounds such as formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, formamide, formic acid, acetone, and acetic acid is similarly low.

Overall, the observed stability in emissions after activating the IC contrasts with the findings reported by Liu et al. [42], which reported a reduction in the amine aerosol emissions with intercooling. It is plausible that the highly controlled test environment limited the visible effects of the IC. This could suggest intercooling may not always serve as an effective mitigation strategy. To better understand the impact of IC, additional testing under more varied operating conditions over more extended periods is recommended.

3.3.2. Impact of reboiler duty and IC shutdown on absorber temperature and emissions

The reboiler duty is the energy supplied to the system to regenerate the solvent. Adjusting the heat input controls the temperature and vapor flow inside the plant, specifically in the stripper, where the solvent is regenerated. Higher reboiler duty results in lower lean solvent loading, thereby enhancing CO₂ capture efficiency. However, it also increases energy consumption and exposes the solvent to higher thermal conditions, which can accelerate thermal degradation if maintained over long

durations [68,70]. Therefore, careful tuning of the reboiler duty is crucial to maximize capture without compromising energy efficiency or solvent stability.

During the measuring campaign, the reboiler duty was reduced by 2 kW to observe any immediate effects on emissions. The setpoint was changed on April 27th at 04:56 and reverted on April 29th at 09:42. Operationally, this adjustment resulted in a decrease in temperature in the lower section of the desorber and an increase in lean solvent loading during that period. As expected, the temperature of the solvent entering the absorber remained constant at 31.2 ± 0.5 °C throughout the reboiler duty adjustment. The stripper pressure remained steady during the whole period at 0.8 barg.

The change of the reboiler set point resulted in little to no immediate change in the measured emission compounds. However, returning the reboiler duty to its original setpoint decreased the lean solvent loading. This change coincided with the IC being turned off at 12:19 later that day. The reduced lean loading allowed for more capture capacity, resulting in a rise in temperature in the middle section of the absorber. Specifically, the temperature at the top of the bed increased from 64.4 ± 0.6 °C before the intercooler tests and reboiler change to 70.1 ± 1.4 °C afterwards.

The rise in absorber temperatures corresponds with a reduction in MNPZ emissions by approximately 90% for the remainder of the measuring campaign, as shown in Fig. 15b. This downward trend suggests a potential link between increased thermal conditions and MNPZ formation and emission. These findings are consistent with the observations reported by Voice et al. [71], which found that nitrosamine thermal decomposition occurred in cycling systems, like the one used for this study. However, further investigation of increased absorber temperatures is necessary to fully understand the extent and reliability of this mitigation strategy and the effect on other emission compounds.

3.3.3. Impact of solvent filter on amine emissions

To maintain solvent integrity and minimize operational issues such as foaming and fouling, the MTU is equipped with an activated carbon filter. It is positioned downstream of the lean cooler and upstream of the absorber column. By continuously removing impurities and degradation products from the solvent, the filter contributes to a more stable operating environment and may influence emission behavior during extended operation. In previous work, the activated carbon solvent filter proved highly effective in resolving foaming issues. It also had a marked effect on solvent quality, as its use transformed the solvent from a dark yellow color to nearly colorless after filtration [72].

Furthermore, the solvent filter has a minor role in increasing the lean solvent temperature prior to it entering the absorber. During the campaign, when the solvent filter was connected, the solvent entering the absorber maintained a temperature of 31.3 ± 0.8 °C. After the filter was disconnected, the lean solvent temperature was 28.0 ± 1.1 °C.

During the Skærbækværket campaign, the solvent filter was in operation and had a steady lean solvent flow of 100 kg/h. For the duration of the gas measuring period, the lean solvent flow was 203.5 ± 27.7 kg/h, and the rich solvent flow was kept at 220 ± 4.35 kg/h. The fluctuations in the lean solvent flow are due to the system's control deadband in the flow control valve, which was fixed during a later campaign.

To test the effect of the solvent filter on reducing emissions, the filter was temporarily bypassed on April 30th at 12:30, as indicated by the black vertical line, on Fig. 18. For the duration of the solvent filter test, the wash tower was actively cooled to maintain the plant's water balance. In Fig. 18, the period of active cooling is highlighted by the light blue shaded area. The corresponding effect on the temperature of the bottom section of the wash tower (Bed 1) is illustrated by the light blue temperature profile. The gap in the emission measurements on April 30th, between 09:26 and 10:02, corresponds to the PTR-ToF-MS calibration period.

After the solvent filter was bypassed, AMP concentration displayed a

Fig. 18. a) Emissions [ppbv] (left axis) and wash bed 1 temperature [°C] (right axis) over time during the bypass of the solvent filter for: a) AMP, b) PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ, c) other solvent-specific degradation products. Emission measurements are considered semi-quantitative.

consistent increase over the entire testing duration, with only temporary dips corresponding to cooling phases, as illustrated on Fig. 18a. For the duration that the solvent filter was bypassed, AMP emissions showed a clear and substantial rise by approximately 400%, illustrating the effectiveness of the solvent filter in reducing AMP emissions when the system remains in steady operation. After the solvent filter was reinstated and flow was routed through it, on May 1st at 08:45, AMP emissions exhibited an immediate decline, before the PTR-ToF-MS was

Table 3

Semi-quantitative amine measurements and compound level changes before and after the bypassing of the solvent filter.

Compounds	Solvent filter on [ppbv]	Solvent filter off [ppbv]	Change on to off [%]	Reduction, off to on [%]
NH ₄	675	1034	53.1	34.7
Formaldehyde	17.3	19.5	12.5	11.1
Acetonitrile	16.1	16.5	2.0	2.0
Acetaldehyde	23.9	27.2	13.9	12.2
Formamide	23.5	23.6	0.4	0.4
Formic Acid	7.8	9.6	23.5	19.0
Acetone	666.1	528.6	-20.6	-26.0
Acetic Acid	11.4	15.4	34.7	25.8
AMP	33.6	178.0	429.2	81.1
Methyl-AMP	9.0	214.5	2278.8	95.8
PZ	1.2	4.6	268.1	72.8
methyl-PZ	0.3	0.2	-11.2	-12.6
NPIP	2.4	4.7	96.4	49.1
MNPZ	0.7	0.6	-13.3	-15.4
DNPZ	0.6	0.5	-17.2	-20.7
PZ-NO ₂	0.6	0.5	-12.4	-14.2
Piperidine	2.9	2.7	-6.1	-6.5
CH ₃ NO ₂	0.9	0.9	8.4	7.8
C ₃ H ₈ O ₂	10.0	5.5	-45.3	-82.8
C ₅ H ₆ O	0.5	0.6	15.0	13.1
Morpholine	15.7	24.6	56.8	36.2
Acetylmorpholine	1.6	1.2	-21.7	-27.7

disconnected.

PZ showed emission behavior similar to AMP throughout the test period. PZ presented a consistent increase over the testing duration, with only temporary dips corresponding to cooling phases, as illustrated by the blue line on Fig. 18b. During that period, PZ increased by approximately 200% to the highest level recorded throughout the entire testing campaign. However, like AMP, PZ levels showed an immediate decline after the solvent filter was reconnected, with the concentration still decreasing before the ToF-MS was disconnected.

As indicated in Table 3, most of the measured compounds exhibited a response to the bypassing of the solvent filter, like that of the solvent amines. Though measured, dinitropiperazine is not presented in Table 3, due to it being at almost non-detectable levels, throughout the entire campaign.

The effect on bypassing the solvent filter is most apparent on the concentration of methyl-AMP, which exhibited a substantial increase in concentration, increasing sharply during the bypass period, as illustrated by the red line on Fig. 18c. This indicates that the utilization of the solvent filter resulted in a 95.8% reduction of methyl-AMP emissions. Other compounds, such as NH₄, formaldehyde, acetonitrile, acetaldehyde, formamide, formic acid, acetic acid, PZ-related compound NPIP, morpholine, and chemical formations CH₃NO₂ and C₅H₆O, also displayed an increase in concentration when the solvent filter was circumvented.

As shown in Table 3, not all compounds increased when the solvent filter was disconnected, with a few compounds decreasing during that period. Acetone and acetylmorpholine concentrations presented an opposite behavior to that of AMP and PZ, with both compounds presenting a decreasing trend when the solvent filter was removed. Additionally, unlike PZ, most of the PZ-related compounds displayed a decrease during that period. However, as most of these compounds were detected at very low concentrations, the observed changes may be attributed to operational variability rather than a direct effect of the solvent filter.

Fig. 19. a) Impurities [ppbv] (left axis) and IC flow [kg/h] (right axis) over time at the CO₂-rich stream for: a) AMP, b) PZ, MNPZ, and DNPZ, c) other solvent-specific degradation products. Emission measurements are considered semi-quantitative.

Overall, the results indicate that the implementation of the solvent filter has a valuable role in controlling amine emissions. When the solvent filter was bypassed, emission of AMP, PZ, and several other byproducts increased noticeably. More specifically, this suggests that rather than simply reducing concentrations, the solvent filter helps prevent the accumulation and release of amine byproducts, proving to be an effective mitigation strategy for amine-based carbon capture plants. However, further research could help identify the filters' potential life span and challenges.

3.4. CO₂ gas stream impurities

Impurities in the CO₂-rich stream, originating from solvent regeneration in the stripper, provide crucial insight into solvent behavior and the effectiveness of emission control strategies. These impurities can affect the purity of the captured CO₂ gas stream and can cause implications for any downstream utilization or permanent storage [73]. The results demonstrate how operational factors such as pump fluctuations and the use of IC can influence emissions and overall system performance.

3.4.1. Influence of intercooling on impurities in the CO₂-rich stream

The IC is employed to enhance CO₂ capture efficiency by lowering the solvent temperature in the absorber, which may, in turn, affect the extent of the reaction and solvent degradation. Studies have also reported a reduction in the amine impurities in the depleted gas stream when IC is employed [22,42]. However, the results indicate that IC may cause impurities to shift from the treated gas to the CO₂ stream, as solvent changes can alter the release of volatile compounds.

To investigate the effect of the IC on the CO₂ stream impurities, the ToF-MS measurement system was utilized. The IC was employed on May 1st at 10:54. At this time, intermittent fluctuations in the lean solvent flow control valve caused instability in the lean solvent flow rate. The deadband of the control valve was, at this period of operation, higher than usual. This impacted the system's stability, subsequently affecting

Table 4

Semiquantitative amine-related emissions measured in the different streams.

Compound	CO ₂ -rich stream emissions [ppbv]	Wash Tower IC emissions [ppbv]	Deviation [ppbv]
Formaldehyde	581.5 ± 57.3	38.2	543.3
Acetonitrile	132.4 ± 6.6	24.9	107.4
Acetaldehyde	4692.1 ± 377.0	43.2	4648.8
Formamide	44.4 ± 1.5	24.0	20.4
Formic Acid	15.8 ± 1.2	9.2	6.6
Acetone	4281.4 ± 151.3	447.3	3834.1
Acetic Acid	49.2 ± 2.4	12.7	36.6
CH ₃ NO ₂	6.3 ± 0.1	0.7	5.5
C ₃ H ₆ O ₂	2.2 ± 0.3	9.5	-7.4
C ₅ H ₆ O	2.0 ± 1.1	0.8	1.2
PZ	68.1 ± 1.7	1.3	66.8
Morpholine	81.0 ± 38.4	22.9	58.1
AMP	39.4 ± 10.2	14.3	25.1
Methyl-PZ	0.4 ± 0.0	0.3	0.1
Methyl-AMP	23.0 ± 5.0	1.6	21.3
NPIP	3.0 ± 0.4	2.1	0.9
MNPZ	70.9 ± 25.4	2.2	68.8
Acetylmorpholine	2.6 ± 1.5	1.7	0.9
DNPZ	0.4 ± 0.0	0.9	-0.5

the absorber's liquid flow stability. The unstable presence of solvent in the absorber column resulted in fluctuations in the rich pump and the IC pump. These fluctuations are also reflected in the gas measurements.

During the period of IC pump fluctuations, which lasted until May 1st at 21:10, the emissions escaping with the CO₂ stream remained stable. The minor variations observed mostly aligning with IC flow intervals, as shown in Fig. 19. Over this period, almost all measured compounds showed higher emission levels in the CO₂ compared to the depleted gas when the IC was in operation.

The lean solvent fluctuations subsided after May 1st 21:10, as illustrated in Fig. 19. At this point, fluctuations were reduced to an extent for the IC to operate consistently, at a flow rate of 175.9 ± 1.2 kg/h. As the IC flow became more stable, some measured compounds exhibited an

increase in concentration on the CO₂-rich stream. The observed shift in impurity levels is likely due to the IC operation, which maintains the impurities in solution that would otherwise be released with the depleted gas. However, since the degradation kinetics remain unchanged, the emission source shifts from the absorber to the stripper.

In the case of AMP, the spike was temporary, followed by a downward trend, as shown in Fig. 19a. A similar pattern was observed for methyl-AMP and formamide, as shown in Fig. 19c. Of the measured compounds, acetylmorpholine also exhibited a downward trend following the spike, although not shown in the figure.

As shown in Fig. 19b, following an initial increase after implementation of the IC operation, PZ, DNPZ, and MNPZ impurity levels did not decrease and instead remained relatively stable in terms of ppbv. Similarly, several other compounds, including formaldehyde, acetonitrile, acetaldehyde, formic acid, acetone, morpholine, acetic acid, methyl-PZ, and NPIP, also exhibited stable behavior, with selected examples shown in Fig. 19c.

Generally, the findings indicate that the initiation of IC strongly influences the concentration of impurities in the CO₂ stream. The results suggest a potential shift in impurities from the absorber to the stripper upon the application of the IC. However, further investigation is needed to fully understand how these changes impact overall process efficiency and emission response.

3.4.2. Influence of solvent circulation on impurities in the CO₂-rich stream

Fluctuations in the operation of rich and lean solvent pumps affect the overall system performance and can impact impurity levels in the various gas streams. The deadband of the lean solvent flow control valve caused minor fluctuations in the rich solvent pump, in addition to variations in the IC flow. During that period, the rich pump provided a flow rate of 219.9 ± 10.5 kg/h. The pump fluctuations ceased a few hours later, on May 1st at 23:04, as indicated by the red line on Fig. 19, after which the flow stabilized at 219.9 ± 1.1 kg/h.

The fluctuations in impurity levels became visible after the stabilization of the IC flow, on May 1st at 21:10. However, although the spikes in the impurity levels in the CO₂ appear to occur at similar frequencies with plant operational fluctuations, detailed analysis confirms there is no causal correlation.

Following the stabilization of the rich solvent flow, the AMP levels began to increase, as shown in Fig. 19a. Similar upward trends were also observed for acetonitrile, morpholine, acetylmorpholine, DNPZ, NPIP, acetaldehyde, as well as the compound with the chemical formation of C₅H₆O.

The increase in these compounds can be attributed to improved solvent circulation, which facilitates the potential shift in emissions from the absorber to the stripper, thereby solidifying the results presented earlier in this section.

3.4.3. Measured compounds in CO₂-rich stream

The CO₂-rich stream was measured to assess impurity levels carried over from the solvent and to evaluate the performance of the desorption. These measurements lasted for approximately 10 hours until the biomass-fired boiler '402' ramped down on May 2nd at approximately 02:00. That resulted in the temporary stop of flue gas flow and the end of the measuring period. The impurities measured in the CO₂ stream, before the stabilization of the IC flow, along with their corresponding standard deviations, as measured and are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 clearly shows that a greater amount of impurities were released with the CO₂-rich stream compared to those from the absorber when the IC was in operation. However, it is also important to note that the solvent filter was active during this period, which effectively reduces emissions, as previously discussed.

Specifically for the solvent amines, AMP concentration was measured approximately 63% higher on the CO₂-rich side. In comparison, PZ was detected at 68.1 ± 1.7 ppbv, representing an increase of 97% compared to the depleted stream, as shown in Table 4. AMP-related

emissions, such as methyl-AMP and acetone, also showed elevated concentrations in the CO₂-rich gas, with acetone measured approximately 90% higher compared to the depleted gas stream. Most PZ-related emissions similarly exhibited elevated concentrations on the rich gas stream, with MNPZ being the most notable, with an increase of 97%.

Generally, nearly all measured compounds exhibited increased concentrations in the CO₂ stream compared to the depleted gas stream, with acetaldehyde showing the highest increase, of approximately 99%. Overall, the results indicate a potential redistribution of emissions from the absorber to the desorber with the implementation of the IC. However, it is also essential to recognize that the emission levels measured in the depleted gas stream are affected by the solvent filter process, which influences the overall emission profile. Although this shift could significantly impact process operations and emission control strategies, more detailed studies over longer periods are necessary to fully understand these effects.

4. Conclusions

This work presents the influence of flue gas composition, wash column operation, and process configurations, and emission behavior of a carbon capture unit utilizing CESAR1 at a biomass-fired power plant. The results provide practical insights into how variations in flue gas oxygen levels, the wash column operational stability, and process adjustments directly influence amine emissions, highlighting critical areas for operational optimization and emission control.

The findings indicate that the swift in flue gas composition had a notable role in influencing amine emissions. Specifically, the increase in AMP and PZ emissions appears to result from slight foaming following the gas composition shift, which enhances solvent carryover. Highlighting the importance of monitoring and managing flue gas composition to control amine emissions in amine-based carbon capture systems, as even minor changes can significantly influence emission behavior.

Furthermore, we demonstrate that the wash column's operational conditions, specifically water flow rate, temperature, and acid concentration, play a critical role in controlling amine emissions. The results highlight that emissions mirror variations in water wash flow, with the relationship most pronounced during steady operation. Temperature variations of the wash beds, especially during periods of active cooling, significantly influence amine emissions.

Acid concentration of the acid wash is an effective mitigation strategy, but only when maintained at low pH levels. At high pH levels, the solutions behaved more as a buffer rather than a reactive agent. This could suggest that a controlled acid dosing system capable of maintaining a consistently low pH could provide more consistent and effective emission control.

Process configurations have a crucial role in managing amine emissions within amine-based carbon capture systems. The activation of the IC showed little impact on emission levels in the depleted gas stream under the controlled conditions of this study, contrasting with some previous findings. However, further investigation over extended periods and a wider range of operating scenarios is necessary to fully understand its actual effect on emissions. Despite this, shutting down the IC in conjunction with an increase in the reboiler duty resulted in increased absorber temperatures. This led to significant changes in the absorber emission profile, notably a reduction in MNPZ levels.

Employing the solvent filter proved highly effective in controlling amine emissions by preventing the accumulation and subsequent release of byproducts, demonstrating its efficacy as an effective emission mitigation strategy. These findings suggest that careful optimization of process configurations is crucial for achieving both emission control and optimal operational performance.

The overall results indicated that the most effective way to control emissions in the depleted gas was when employing the solvent filter in combination with the circulating acid loop, optimally maintained at pH

3. The study indicates that adopting and pairing advanced process configurations can reduce emissions to very low, almost non-detectable levels.

The CO₂-rich stream was analyzed for impurity concentrations, while the IC was employed. The results indicate that the initiation of the IC significantly affected impurity levels in the CO₂-rich stream, with nearly all measured compounds exhibiting higher concentrations compared to the CO₂-depleted gas stream. Initiating IC appears to cause a redistribution of impurities from the absorber to the stripper. However, a more detailed investigation is needed to fully understand the extent of this shift and its implications for process efficiency and emission control.

In summary, the results highlight the complexity of amine emissions and emphasize the importance of ongoing optimization of operational parameters to enhance emission control and overall system performance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Maria Dimitriadi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christina Andersen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Isaac Appelquist Løge:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Randi Neerup:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Søren Jensen:** Writing – review & editing. **Jakob Lindkvist Karlsson:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Pantelis Bountzidis:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Nomiki Kottaki:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Frantz Bræstrup:** Writing – review & editing. **Kristian Røhe Kongst Krum:** Writing – review & editing. **Søren Christensen:** Writing – review & editing. **Sebastian Nis Bay Villadsen:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jens Abildskov:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Philip Loldrup Fosbøl:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Author contributions

All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT and Grammarly in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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